

VISCOELASTIC SHEAR LAG ANALYSIS OF THE DISCONTINUOUS FIBER COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Many models have been developed to predict homogenized material properties for fiber-reinforced composite materials. For dilute systems, Eshelby's[1] elegant elasticity solution of the equivalent inclusion problem provides the foundation for this work. The Mori-Tanaka[2] model provides predictions for more concentrated systems. A heuristic model, popular for its simplicity, is the Halpin-Tsai[3] model which predicts a variety of composite properties with a single coefficient. All of these models are very useful for finding the overall homogenized elastic properties, but yield little insight to stress-transfer between the fiber and the matrix.

The so-called "shear lag" model, developed by Cox[4] as a solution for a single discontinuous fiber embedded in a matrix, is also popular due to its simplicity. While some of its assumptions limit its accuracy[5], shear lag does yield valuable insight into both the homogenized material properties and the stress-transfer region between the fiber and matrix.

All of the above models were developed assuming elastic materials for both fiber and matrix. Over short time scales and at temperatures well below the glass transition, this is a good approximation. At elevated temperatures, or long time scales, however, creep and stress relaxation phenomena are important[6].

To model the time-dependent properties of a composite material, it becomes necessary to

include time-dependent material properties and to solve the analogous problem with viscoelasticity. As an initial solution, and to gain insight into the micromechanical behavior present, the present paper follows the elastic solution for a discontinuous fiber suspended in an elastic matrix developed by Cox[4], introducing a viscoelastic matrix material, while assuming the reinforcing fibers to remain elastic.

2 Viscoelastic Analysis

2.1 Time-dependence: Stress Relaxation

Consider the elastic solution for a discontinuous fiber of length $2L$ and radius r suspended in an elastic matrix and submitted to an axial strain ϵ_x as described by the traditional shear-lag model[4] shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The RVE for the shear-lag formulation used in this paper.

To solve the Shear Lag Problem for a viscoelastic material, the correspondence principle is invoked. As shown by Lee[7] and Biot[8], equivalent viscoelastic equations can be found for isotropic or anisotropic materials utilizing an elastic analysis.

The relationship between the axial stress, σ_f , and the shear traction at the fiber surface, τ_i , is given in (1). Here the stress components are taken as functions of the spatial coordinate in the fiber direction, x , and time, t . The fiber radius is r_0 .

$$\frac{d\sigma_f(x, t)}{dx} = -\frac{2\tau_i(x, t)}{r_0} \quad (1)$$

By equating the shear forces on adjacent annuli, a relationship can be found between the shear traction, τ_i , and the shear stress at some distance, r , from the center line of the fiber.

$$\tau(t) = \frac{r_0}{r} \tau_i(t) \quad (2)$$

For a viscoelastic material, the shear stress can be expressed as a function of the instantaneous Shear Modulus, $G_m(t)$, and the strain rate, $\frac{d\gamma}{dt'}$, as shown in (3), where γ is the shear strain.

$$\tau(t) = \int_0^t G_m(t-t') \frac{d\gamma}{dt'} dt' \quad (3)$$

Assuming that the shear strain, γ , is equal to $\frac{du}{dr}$, where u is the axial displacement, and differentiating with respect to t' :

$$\frac{d\gamma}{dt'} = \frac{d}{dt'} \left(\frac{du}{dr} \right) \quad (4)$$

Substituting (4) into (3) and subsequently substituting into (2) yields:

$$\tau_i(t) \frac{r_0}{r} dr = \int_0^t G_m(t-t') \frac{du}{dt'} dt' \quad (5)$$

Integrating from the edge of the fiber ($r = r_0$) to the far-field location, R , yields:

$$\tau_i(t) = \frac{1}{r_0 \ln\left(\frac{R}{r_0}\right)} \int_0^t G_m(t-t') \frac{d}{dt'} (u_R - u_{r_0}) dt' \quad (6)$$

Substituting (6) into (1) yields:

$$\frac{d\sigma_f(x, t)}{dx} = -\frac{2}{r_0^2 \ln\left(\frac{R}{r_0}\right)} \int_0^t G_m(t-t') \frac{d}{dt'} (u_R - u_{r_0}) dt' \quad (7)$$

Differentiation with respect to x and substitution of strain-displacement relations:

$$\frac{d^2\sigma_f(x, t)}{dx^2} = -\frac{2}{r_0^2 \ln\left(\frac{R}{r_0}\right)} \int_0^t G_m(t-t') \frac{d}{dt'} (\epsilon_R - \epsilon_{r_0}) dt' \quad (8)$$

If a perfect bond between the fiber and matrix is assumed, ϵ_{r_0} can be replaced with ϵ_f . It is also assumed that the far-field strain, ϵ_R is far enough from the fiber that it is identical to the applied strain, ϵ_1 .

$$\frac{d^2\sigma_f(x, t)}{dx^2} = -\frac{2}{r_0^2 \ln\left(\frac{R}{r_0}\right)} \int_0^t G_m(t-t') \frac{d}{dt'} (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_f) dt' \quad (9)$$

Assuming the fiber to be perfectly elastic and also assuming that the transverse and radial stresses are negligible when compared to the axial stress, ϵ_f can be replaced with $\frac{\sigma_f}{E_f}$.

$$\frac{d^2\sigma_f(x, t)}{dx^2} = -\frac{2}{r_0^2 \ln\left(\frac{R}{r_0}\right)} \int_0^t G_m(t-t') \left(\frac{d\epsilon_1}{dt'} - \frac{1}{E_f} \frac{d\sigma_f(t)}{dt'} \right) dt' \quad (10)$$

A Laplace Transform can be performed on (10) to transform the convolution integral into a simple multiplication.

$$\frac{d^2\sigma_f(s)}{dx^2} = -\frac{2}{r_0^2 \ln\left(\frac{R}{r_0}\right)} G_m(s) \left(s\epsilon_1(s) + \epsilon_1(+0) - \frac{s\sigma_f(s)}{E_f} \right) \quad (11)$$

This is a second-order linear differential equation of a standard form with the solution:

$$\sigma_f(s) = A \sinh\left(\frac{n^* x}{r_0}\right) + B \cosh\left(\frac{n^* x}{r_0}\right) + \left[E_f \epsilon_1(s) + \frac{E_f}{s} \epsilon_1(+0) \right] \quad (12)$$

Where:

$$n^* = \sqrt{\frac{2sG_m(s)}{E_f \ln\left(\frac{R}{r_0}\right)}} \quad (13)$$

Applying the boundary condition of zero fiber stress at the fiber terminations ($\sigma_f = 0$ at $x=\pm L$) yields:

$$\sigma_f(s) = \left[E_f \epsilon_1(s) + \frac{E_f}{s} \epsilon_1(+0) \right] \left\{ 1 - \cosh\left(\frac{n^*x}{r_0}\right) \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{n^*L}{r_0}\right) \right\} \quad (14)$$

Since determination of the global average stress within the body, σ_x , is essential to determine the overall composite response, it is necessary to determine the average fiber stress over its length, $2L$, $\bar{\sigma}_f$.

$$\bar{\sigma}_f(s) = \frac{1}{2L} \int_{-L}^L \sigma_f(s) dx \quad (15)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_f(s) = \left[E_f \epsilon_1(s) + \frac{E_f}{s} \epsilon_1(+0) \right] \left\{ 1 - \frac{\tanh(n^*L/r_0)}{n^*L/r_0} \right\} \quad (16)$$

If the global stress is assumed to be found by a simple rule of mixtures relationship ($\sigma_1 = \nu_f \bar{\sigma}_f + (1 - \nu_f) \bar{\sigma}_m$), then σ_1 can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_1 = \nu_f \left[E_f \epsilon_1(s) + \frac{E_f}{s} \epsilon_1(+0) \right] \left\{ 1 - \frac{\tanh(n^*L/r_0)}{n^*L/r_0} \right\} + (1 - \nu_f) \bar{\sigma}_m \quad (17)$$

Since there is no closed-form solution for an inverse Laplace transform of an equation of this form, it must be integrated numerically. A simple and computationally efficient algorithm was developed by Trefethen et al.[9] and adapted for use in this problem.

2.2 Time-dependence: Creep

A similar formulation can be developed by relating the shear strain to the instantaneous creep compliance, $J_m(t)$, and the shear stress rate.

$$\gamma(t) = \int_0^t J_m(t-t') \frac{d}{dt'} [\tau(t)] dt' \quad (18)$$

Following the same approach as outlined in (1) - (17), the fiber strain is determined as follows:

$$\epsilon_1 - \frac{\sigma_f}{E_f} = - \int_0^t J_m(t-t') \frac{d}{dt'} \left[\frac{r_0^2 \ln(R/r_0)}{2} \frac{d^2 \sigma_f(t)}{dx^2} \right] dt' \quad (19)$$

Again, performing a Laplace Transform yields a second-order ordinary differential equation:

$$\epsilon_1(s) - \frac{\sigma_f(s)}{E_f} = -J_m(s) \frac{r_0^2 \ln(R/r_0) s}{2} \frac{d^2 \sigma_f(s)}{dx^2} \quad (20)$$

With the solution:

$$\sigma_f(s) = E_f \epsilon_1 \left\{ 1 - \cosh\left(\frac{n^{creep} x}{r_0}\right) \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{n^{creep} L}{r_0}\right) \right\} \quad (21)$$

This is similar to the stress relaxation solution, with the exception that n^{creep} is given by:

$$n^{creep} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{E_f J_m(s) \ln(R/r_0) s}} \quad (22)$$

As before the average fiber stress is found by integration:

$$\bar{\sigma}_f(s) = E_f \epsilon_1(s) \left\{ 1 - \frac{\tanh\left(\frac{n^{creep} L}{r_0}\right)}{\frac{n^{creep} L}{r_0}} \right\} \quad (23)$$

In the creep formulation, however, the input global stress is related to an output strain, hence:

$$\sigma_1 = \nu_f \bar{\sigma}_f + (1 - \nu_f) \bar{\sigma}_m \quad (24)$$

Substituting Hooke's Law for a viscoelastic material in creep yields:

$$\sigma_1(t) = \nu_f \bar{\sigma}_f + (1 - \nu_f) \int_0^t \frac{1}{D_m(t-t')} \frac{d\epsilon}{dt'} dt' \quad (25)$$

And performing a Laplace transform to handle the convolution integral:

$$\sigma_1(s) = \nu_f \bar{\sigma}_f + (1 - \nu_f) \frac{\epsilon_1(s) s}{D_m(s)} \quad (26)$$

Which can be expressed in terms of ϵ_1 :

$$\sigma_1(s) = \nu_f E_f \epsilon_1(s) \left[1 - \frac{\tanh(n^{creep} L/r_0)}{n^{creep} L/r_0} \right] + (1 - \nu_f) \frac{\epsilon_1(s) s}{D_m(s)} \quad (27)$$

Solving for ϵ_1 and including the time-zero-value of σ_1 yields:

$$\epsilon_1(s) = \frac{\sigma_1(s) + \frac{1}{s}\sigma_1(+0)}{v_f E_f \left[1 - \frac{\tanh(n^{creep} L/r_0)}{n^{creep} L/r_0} \right] + \frac{(1-v_f)s}{D_m}} \quad (28)$$

2.3 Frequency Domain

It is desirable to develop a frequency domain solution. The following derivation follows a similar derivation used by Sims and Halpin[6] to equate separate experiments for composites. Recall Hooke's law for creep (shown here in tension):

$$\epsilon(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t S(t-t') \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t'} dt' \quad (29)$$

Where S(t) is the creep compliance.

For a sinusoidal input stress, σ , of frequency ω :

$$\sigma(t) = E_0 e^{i\omega t} \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t'} = E_0 i\omega e^{i\omega t'} \quad (31)$$

Substituting (31) into (29):

$$\epsilon(t) = E_0 i\omega \int_{-\infty}^t S(t-t') e^{i\omega t'} dt' \quad (32)$$

Change variables: $u = t - t'$

$$\epsilon(t) = E_0 i\omega \int_{\infty}^0 S(u) e^{i\omega(t-u)} (-du) \quad (33)$$

$$\epsilon(t) = E_0 i\omega e^{i\omega t} \int_0^{\infty} S(u) e^{-i\omega u} du \quad (34)$$

Dividing by $\sigma(t)$ and converting to trigonometric form:

$$\frac{\epsilon(t)}{\sigma(t)} = i\omega \int_0^{\infty} S(u) [\cos(\omega u) - i\sin(\omega u)] du \quad (35)$$

The storage, J_1 , and loss, J_2 , compliances can now be defined as:

$$J_1 = \omega \int_0^{\infty} S(u) \sin(\omega u) du \quad (36)$$

$$J_2 = \omega \int_0^{\infty} S(u) \cos(\omega u) du \quad (37)$$

Where the complex compliance, J^* ($\epsilon(\omega) = J^* \sigma(\omega)$):

$$J^* = J_1 - iJ_2 \quad (38)$$

As before for the time-domain solution, the integrals in (36) and (37) will generally be evaluated numerically.

2.4 Frequency Domain Calculation Example

To simplify the calculation of the improper integral in Equations (36) and (37), a curve can be fit to the time-domain creep data of the form:

$$S(t) = at^b \quad (39)$$

Substituting (39) for S(t) in (36) and (37) gives the following:

$$J_1 = \omega \int_0^{\infty} at^b \sin(\omega u) du \quad (40)$$

$$J_2 = \omega \int_0^{\infty} at^b \cos(\omega u) du \quad (41)$$

These can be evaluated explicitly using the gamma function, which was demonstrated by Lebedev and Halpin[10].

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-cu} u^d du = \frac{\Gamma(d+1)}{c^{d+1}} \quad (42)$$

Where $\Gamma(d+1)$ represents the gamma function. To utilize this relationship, let $c = i\omega$:

$$e^{-cu} = \cos(\omega u) - i\sin(\omega u) \quad (43)$$

Also:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{c^{d+1}} &= c^{-d-1} = (i\omega)^{-d-1} = \left(\omega e^{\frac{i\pi}{2}} \right)^{-d-1} \\ &= -i(\omega)^{-d-1} \left(\cos\left(\frac{d\pi}{2}\right) - i\sin\left(\frac{d\pi}{2}\right) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Finally, multiplying (38) by $-i$:

$$-iJ_1 + J_2 = -i\omega \int_0^{\infty} at^b \sin(\omega u) du \quad (45)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ \omega \int_0^{\infty} at^b \cos(\omega u) du \\ &= a\omega^{-b} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-i\omega t} t^b dt \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

This is now in the form presented in (42) with $c = i\omega$, $u = t$ and $d = b$ therefore, using (44) and (42):

$$-iJ_1 + J_2 = a\omega^{-b} \left(-i \cos\left(\frac{b\pi}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{b\pi}{2}\right) \Gamma(1+b) \right) \quad (47)$$

The real and imaginary parts can then be separated to find J_1 and J_2 independently. To perform this procedure in reverse (for example, to obtain the creep compliance curve of a material only using dynamic experiments), a curve of the form $J_1(\omega) = c\omega^{-b}$ would need to be fit to the experimental data. This curve fit will automatically provide the b used for the time-domain compliance $S(t) = at^b$, since the only power of ω found in (47) is $-b$. It is then simple algebra to find a :

$$a = \frac{J_1}{\omega^{-b} \cos\left(\frac{b\pi}{2}\right) \Gamma(1+b)} \quad (48)$$

To identify the proper range of frequencies over which to perform an experiment, it is helpful to develop a relation such that $S(t) = J_1(\omega)$. If the compliance, $S(t)$, is again assumed to have a power law form:

$$at^b = \left(a\omega^{-b} \cos\left(\frac{b\pi}{2}\right) \right) \Gamma(1+b) \quad (49)$$

The angular frequency can be solved for explicitly:

$$\omega = \frac{\left(\cos\left(\frac{b\pi}{2}\right) \Gamma(1+b) \right)^{\frac{1}{b}}}{t} \quad (50)$$

3 Results

3.1 Boundary Layer

Elastic fiber-matrix shear stress transfer is a boundary layer phenomenon. If the interfacial shear stress, τ_i from the Shear-Lag Model is shown as a function of axial distance, x , normalized by the fiber diameter, D for different fiber aspect ratios ($2L/D$), it can be seen that the stress is identical regardless of aspect ratio. This effect can be referred to as a boundary layer, with all stress transfer occurring within a certain distance from the fiber end. The normalized

shear stress as a function of aspect ratio is shown in Fig. 2 for a material with a fiber volume fraction, v_f , of 0.3, a matrix Poisson's Ratio, ν_m , of 0.3 and ratio of fiber to matrix stiffness, $\frac{E_f}{E_m}$, of 20.

Fig. 2. The boundary layer for interfacial shear stress in the elastic shear-lag model.

The boundary layer can be solved for explicitly if a specific, non-zero value is taken as a threshold zero-value. In the present case, the value of 0.01 was used, which (for the same material properties) yields a constant boundary layer of 5.5 fiber diameters for all fiber lengths greater than two times the boundary layer. For fibers less than two times the boundary layer, there is an insufficient length to develop the full stress profile.

For the viscoelastic Shear-Lag Model, since numerical integration is necessary to obtain a solution, several additional assumptions concerning the material properties must be made. Consider an isotropic viscoelastic matrix material, whose stress relaxation modulus is given as a simple exponential decay function, $E(t) = E_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right)$. The shear stress for several time steps of the solution is plotted with respect to the normalized distance from the end of the fiber, as before, for a fiber with an aspect ratio of 100 is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The effect of a viscoelastic matrix material on the boundary layer for interfacial shear stress.

It is interesting to see that while the peak stress decreases with time, as expected in the stress-relaxation model, shear stress nearer to the center of the fiber actually increases with time, creating a time-sensitive boundary layer that increases with time.

3.2 Stress Relaxation

It is interesting to now examine the viscoelastic shear lag model, varying as many parameters as possible, to demonstrate relationships between the input variables and the properties of the composite. Fig. 4 shows normalized stress relaxation curves for a variation in aspect ratio. The modulus is normalized to more easily compare the different degradation between the different ratios (as opposed to the more obvious difference in actual modulus).

Fig. 4. Normalized stress relaxation for various aspect ratios.

Notice that for aspect ratios of 5 or less, the modulus degrades almost as quickly as the neat matrix. As the fiber length is increased, the composite stress relaxation modulus reduction with time is greatly retarded, even for only 33 % volume fraction of fibers.

It is also interesting to examine the influence of fiber volume fraction. Fig. 5 shows a similar plot, but the fiber aspect ratio is held constant at 20, while fiber volume fraction is varied from 0 to 60%. It is significant that, in this case, the degradation of the modulus of a composite shows very little dependence on the volume fraction, so when modulus degradation is the primary concern, a small percentage of very long fibers could suffice.

Fig. 5. Normalized stress relaxation for various fiber volume fractions

3.3 Creep

As should be expected, the normalized creep results for variation in aspect ratio, shown in Fig. 6, appear similar to the stress-relaxation results (although inverted).

Fig. 6. The effect of varying aspect ratio on creep compliance. Note that the creep compliance is normalized as a percentage of the maximum modulus, to more easily compare between different aspect ratios.

4 Conclusion

The simplicity of the Shear-Lag model lends itself well to adaptation for a viscoelastic solution. Valuable insight is gained both at the microscopic and macroscopic levels by a close examination of the interfacial shear stress and the far-field stress and strain.

From the interfacial shear stress, the local effects of a viscoelastic matrix material continuously increase the boundary layer length wherein stress transfer occurs, compared to the finite boundary layer observed in an elastic matrix.

Far field stress and strain show the global effects of a viscoelastic matrix material, indicating that aspect ratio will have a much stronger effect on the creep and stress relaxation of a fiber-reinforced composite than fiber volume fraction. Volume fraction is still a driving force in determining the magnitude of the modulus, as in the elastic solution, but the modulus degradation and increase in compliance show a much stronger dependence on aspect ratio than volume fraction.

These results all apply to a single fiber embedded in a viscoelastic matrix, aligned with the direction of applied strain. Further work is necessary to examine the viscoelastic properties when fibers are oriented away from the axis of applied strain and how to combine these results for a distribution of fibers, as would be seen in a short-fiber composite. Physical experiments of creep versus aspect ratio and volume fraction are also important to verify the predictions. These will be addressed in future publications.

Fig. 1. The RVE for the shear-lag formulation used in this paper.

Fig. 2. The boundary layer for interfacial shear stress in the elastic shear-lag model.

Fig. 3. The effect of a viscoelastic matrix material on the boundary layer for interfacial shear stress.

Fig. 4. Normalized stress relaxation for various aspect ratios.

Fig. 5. Normalized stress relaxation for various fiber volume fractions

Fig. 6. The effect of varying aspect ratio on creep compliance. Note that the creep compliance is normalized as a percentage

of the maximum modulus, to more easily compare between different aspect ratios.

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